

ENGAGING CITIZENS IN SOIL SCIENCE:
THE ROAD TO HEALTHIER SOILS

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Project information

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Disclaimer

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Foreword

Soil is a vital, yet often disregarded, resource that supports life on Earth by providing the foundation for agriculture, forests, and various other natural ecosystems. However, soil degradation is a growing concern around the world, and it can have severe consequences for our planet like reduced crop yields, increased greenhouse gas emissions, and decreased biodiversity. The ECHO project aims to prevent this by bringing together citizens and volunteer scientists from around Europe to work towards a common goal of protecting and preserving our soils, thus contributing to the transition towards healthy soils of the EU Mission: “A Soil Deal for Europe”.

ECHO will generate new data on the health status of EU soils, complementing existing soil mapping and monitoring in EU Member States and Scotland, including the EU Soil Observatory (EUSO). The project will develop and deploy 28 tailor-made citizen science initiatives across EU Member States and Scotland, taking into account different land-uses, soil types, and biogeographical regions, as well as stakeholder needs. With 16 participants from all over Europe, including 10 leading universities and research centres, 4 SMEs, and 2 Foundations, under the coordination of the Free University of Bolzano-Bozen, ECHO will assess 16,500 sites in different climate and biogeographic regions to achieve its ambitious goals.

The project aims to engage citizens in protecting and restoring soils by building their capacities and enhancing their knowledge. Citizens will thereby not only actively contribute to the project’s data collection but also promote soil stewardship and foster behavioural change across the EU. The ECHOREPO, a long-term open access repository with a direct link to the EUSO, will make the citizen science data available for exploitation not only by scientists but also by citizens, policy makers, farmers, landowners and other end-users, providing added value to existing data and other relevant soil monitoring initiatives. ECHOREPO will thus provide valuable information about the state of soil health in various regions, and help citizens make informed decisions about land use and conservation.

We believe that the ECHO project will have a significant impact on soil health and citizen engagement across Europe and become an important step towards protecting and preserving our soil for future generations. By working together, we can ensure that our soil remains healthy and productive, and that we continue to enjoy the many benefits it provides.

Short description of the deliverable

This document provides a general overview of the structure and contents of the ECHO project website. It reflects, at the time of writing this report, the current status, as well as planned content and features that will be developed along with the project progress during the 4 years lifespan. Possible modifications and improvements might be identified in the future to address any needs not identified at this stage of the project.

This domain <https://echosoil.eu> hosts the website of the ECHO project.

The project partner in charge (PLANTPRESS) has designed the layout, based on WordPress, and will maintain the website content during the project lifetime and at least 6 years after the end of the project. The content updates will be produced mainly as part of WP6 - Dissemination and Communication.

The website will be open to the general public and will be viewable by anyone with access to Internet.

Website aim and goals

The ECHO website is the main communication and dissemination tool to allow stakeholders access to the project development and results. The website also connects the network of project partners and citizen scientists. ECHO's website will host the public dissemination deliverables and citizen science tools, Citizen Science platform including the toolbox and mobile app (WP2) and ECHOREPO digital repository interface (WP5). It will also promote relevant content (reports, articles, videos, leaflets, events) and support monitoring and evaluation activities by providing online surveys and questionnaires.

The ECHO website will be gradually expanded and constantly updated during the lifetime of the project with profiles created on social media (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, TikTok, YouTube).

Language

The main content of the website will be in English, with summary information, project abstract, main outcomes translated in the languages covered by the project consortium (Italian, German, French, Spanish, Portuguese, Greek, Finnish, Polish, Romanian) and available in one of the tabs linking the ECHO website to the websites of the project partners.

Architecture of the website

Home page

The home page is organised according to the following design model:

1. Top of the page (Figure 1):
 - ECHO logo and slogan
 - Main menu
 - Background illustration

Figure 1 – Top of the page

Visitors to our website are welcomed by a dynamic illustration depicting an idyllic view of a sunrise above a golden field. Their attention is drawn to the tumbling hills and the overwhelming importance of soil. The simple and clean style of the illustration evokes a modern feel. The most prominently featured plant - the common dandelion - is native to Europe, and a familiar sight in European cities and fields.

2. Central part of the page (Figure 2)

Figure 2

Below the illustration, there is crucial information about project ECHO in a digestible format. We've outlined our most important Activities and Tools, Outcomes, as well as the answer to the question - Why is ECHO important? Visitors of the website will also see a counter which shows the project's scale at a single glance. (Figure 3)

Figure 3

3. Bottom of the page (Figure 4)

The footer, which remains constant on every page, contains necessary disclaimers and logos regarding the funding of the project, as well the ECHO logo and slogan.

Figure 4

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Main menu

The website is divided into the following sections: ABOUT (which links to the home page), PARTNERS, NEWS & EVENTS, RESOURCES and CONTACT. Our slogan - Engaging citizens in soil science: the road to healthier soils - is also featured in the main menu.

Partners

This tab is to show our Partners and the diversity they represent. After a short overview, visitors to the website can observe an illustrated map of Europe. Each of the project's partners' countries is represented by their national flower - such as the wild rose for Romania, lavender for Portugal or poppy for Poland.

The illustration is accompanied by a “legend” which connects the flowers to specific countries and partners.

As the website grows, this tab will also include an easy-to-use, retractable menu with all the partners listed alphabetically, along with a short description and logo they provide.

News & Events

This tab will be - as described on the website - “the best spot for project updates and news”. Here is where we will publish content, which will then be adapted to various social media posts. For now, we’ve included our first major update - the project’s kick-off meeting in Italy.

As the project develops, this tab will also include a way for visitors to sign up to our official newsletter, which will be issued periodically. It will inform target groups of project progress and will contain information on project events, available results and products. It will also include links to the project website and social media.

The Events section will showcase upcoming events organised and attended by ECHO partners. It will also include reports, recaps and photographs of the events that already took place.

Resources

In the near future, this tab will host the most important resources we will provide for Citizen Scientists and all end-users of soil, interested in its health. This will include the following subsections:

Tools - The Citizen Scientist Platform, ECHOREPO and training material for volunteers

Publications - both in peer-reviewed journals and popular publications

Videos - a series of short videos from different countries called "testimonials" will be produced to show people of different ages and backgrounds joining ECHO.

Versioning and contribution history

Version	Date	Modified by	Notes
0.1	29/08/2023	Wiktoria Witek PLANTPRESS	Draft version
0.2	31/08/2023	Wiktoria Witek PLANTPRESS	Final version